

CTSA

Evaluators Survey

2024

**Evaluator Survey Working Group
Summary of Findings**

2024 CTSA Evaluators Survey

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CTSA Evaluators Survey: Executive Summary of Findings

The results of the 2024 Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) Evaluators Survey, conducted by and for the CTSA evaluators, detail current evaluation practices, resources, challenges and facilitators across the CTSA consortium. Sixty-two out of sixty-five CTSA hubs (95.4%) responded, reflecting robust engagement of the network of evaluators in the consortium and their shared commitment to advancing clinical and translational science.

Key survey findings relate to CTSA's organizational practices and priorities. There is considerable variability in evaluation structures, resources, and practices across the CTSA Consortium, with most CTSA hubs maintaining dedicated evaluation teams. However, there is consistent use of formative and summative evaluation practices, and of Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI) approaches. The results also suggest clear priority areas and emerging trends. Assessing the impact of CTSA activities remains among the highest priority of CTSA Evaluators. They expressed significant interest in developing and adopting standardized performance and impact measures that could facilitate both CTSA's local improvements and benchmarking impact across the Consortium. The use of well-established evaluation frameworks designed for use by CTSA hubs, including the Translational Science Benefits Model, is likely to continue increasing in response to these priorities and trends.

- Evident challenges of CTSA evaluation practice include:
 - Impact Measurement: The lack of standardized metrics and definitions of impact limits the ability of evaluators to make consortium-wide comparisons and disseminate robust evidence of impact.
 - Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI): Many evaluators need more tools, methods, and case examples to support CTSA's CQI programs. There is great variation in the use of CQI frameworks.
 - Collaboration Assessment: Evaluators are interested in using more rigorous methods for evaluating and disseminating the outcomes and impact of both CTSA-level and cross-CTSA collaborations.
 - Resource Constraints: Variability in available evaluation resources, both in staffing and expertise, remains a concern for many CTSA evaluators. CTSA evaluators typically lead relatively small teams.
- Evident facilitators of CTSA evaluation practice include:
 - Community Engagement: The high survey participation rate and broadly-based interest in more peer-to-peer engagement and collaboration reflect a well-connected and motivated community.
 - CTSA Evaluation Resources: There is clear interest in the development of standardized evaluation metrics, instruments and toolkits, as well as structured mentoring and training opportunities.
 - Self-Evaluation Process: The self-led longitudinal survey process enabled updates in contacts and improved communications among Evaluators, highlighting the value of their direct engagement.

These results inform specific conclusions and directions for future research. The continuous feedback collected by and from CTSA Evaluators shapes not only evaluation practice at individual CTSA hubs but also the future of evaluation across the CTSA consortium. The challenges and

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facilitators evident in these results present clear directions for future innovation and resource development within this community. The Evaluator Survey Team will review the current survey methodology and design to improve longitudinal data collection and reporting. There is an opportunity to leverage the iterative collection of these data to advocate for and cultivate the standardization of impact metrics, development of shared resources, and creation of new networking and training opportunities. If proven to be effective, this self-evaluation process can also be presented as a potential best practice for use by other federally funded research consortia that support evaluation programs.

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2024 Evaluator Survey Response Summaries

1. Introduction

A. Purpose of the Survey

Since 2009, the Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) program evaluator community has periodically conducted surveys to provide a current picture on the organization, methods, and impact of evaluation in the CTSA hubs. Previous iterations of this independent, peer-led activity were conducted in 2009, 2010, 2012, 2013, 2018, and 2021. Evaluators have reported using survey results to identify changes in evaluation services and resources from other hubs that could enhance evaluation capabilities at their own hubs, as well as the identification of the most frequently used evaluation frameworks and approaches across the network.

The 2024 National Evaluators Survey was designed to gain an overview of the full spectrum of evaluation resources, collect data on evaluation organization and practices and to compare changes in those over time. The survey also incorporated questions regarding hubs' impact evaluation, dissemination and implementation strategies, hub CQI processes, hub use of the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) (Luke, 2018), and engagement with learning health systems as these were identified as emerging topics of interest for CTSA on a national level. The survey included opportunities for the respondents to provide comments regarding evaluation to National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS) and to comment on CTSA evaluation challenges and practices at the respondent's hub.

One of the challenges related to the development of this survey and analysis of responses is the potential impact of the new FOA which implemented the UM1 category for CTSA hubs. Approximately one-half of the hubs were under the requirements stipulated under the UL1 category and one-half under the UM1 category. Although these involved somewhat similar requirements, the UM1 requirements for stronger emphasis on addressing translational sciences could have influenced the structure and priorities for the evaluation team. The analysis identifies differences between the hubs in each category that may have been due to changing requirements.

This version of the survey underwent review at the Indiana University Human Research Protections Program. Having met all criteria, it was deemed exempt from IRB review, continuing review and approval not required under 45 CFR46.104(d), Category 2(ii).

B. Survey Development Process

The CTSA National Program Evaluators Group established the Evaluator Survey Work Group (Work Group) composed of volunteers from nine CTSA hubs (see membership list in Appendix A). The Work Group reviewed previous CTSA evaluator surveys to identify questions of continued interest to the CTSA evaluator community.

The 2024 Survey was divided into multiple sections of related questions. The several sections had been included in prior evaluator surveys. These included:

- Hub composition

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- Evaluation Team Composition
- Research Performance Progress Report Responsibilities
- Evaluation Data Contribution to Hub Decision Making
- Internal Strategic Management Approaches
- Evaluation Tools and Modes of Analysis
- Evaluation Reports Distribution and Use
- Collection of Demographic Data
- Advice to NCATS and Recommendations

As is standard practice, the evaluator survey team developed questions to address current and emerging evaluation responsibilities and opportunities. The 2024 survey included questions to gather information regarding hub initiatives and evaluation team efforts and responsibilities in the following areas:

- Collaboration within and outside hub
- Impact Evaluation
- Translational Science Benefits Model
- Dissemination and Implementation
- Clinical and Translational Science Evaluation
- Continuous Quality Improvement
- Learning Health System Collaboration

In addition to these issues, the survey included an opportunity for respondents to identify basic evaluation needs for new evaluation teams. This information will be used to inform planning for evaluation training and coaching opportunities across the consortium.

Some questions were taken from previous evaluators' surveys and adapted to the current context of the CTSA Consortium. Responses from these questions provide vital information about changes in the structure of the evaluation team, the evaluation methods used, and challenges to CTSA hub evaluation efforts. All the questions from the Special Topics section are new and were added to meet the most pressing informational needs identified by the members of the Working Group.

The final survey instrument was implemented using REDCap (Harris, 2009) electronic data capture tools hosted at Indiana University.

C. Conducting the Survey

The survey was distributed to the list of evaluators on the NCATS CTSA Program Evaluators Group December 3, 2024. Field time was originally scheduled for four weeks with a due date of December 31, 2024. Three follow-up reminder surveys were issued during this time. As out-of-date email addresses were identified, the Survey Team searched for new contacts at those particular CTSA hubs to determine the most appropriate person to receive the survey for completion. To encourage completion and submission of the survey, Survey Team members volunteered to contact colleagues directly. These efforts resulted in the high cooperation rate and additional updates to the list of evaluator contacts for CTSA hubs. In response to a few reported technical difficulties in the reception of the original email containing the single-institutional link and

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a few requests for additional time to complete the survey, the survey team granted extensions. The final survey response was received on March 20, 2025.

D. Analysis Approach

The survey included a total of 45 questions with multiple question formats including multiple choice, rating scales, matrix questions, dropdown lists, short- and long- answer open-ended and self-fill contact forms. Respondents were asked for numerical responses (e.g., count of evaluation team members), agreement ratings (e.g., Likert like), yes/no, lists, short text, and free length responses. With the variety of question formats, the Work Group developed a strategy to analyze and share the data in multiple reports.

This report provides a summary of data from the numerical, scaled, yes/no, and lists questions for the overall CTSA hubs data and a high-level summary of narrative responses to open-ended opportunities.

E. Summary on Number of CTSA's responding compared to Total Number of CTSA's surveyed

The survey was distributed to evaluators at sixty-five CTSA hubs. Of those hubs, sixty-two hub representatives responded to the survey (95.4 percent). Prior iterations of this survey also produced similarly high response rates indicating a significant interest in helping provide updated information about CTSA hub evaluation programs and accomplishments.

Responding CTSA Hub Characteristics

Sixty-two CTSA hubs responded to the 2024 Evaluator Survey and provided at least some data for analysis. Of those hubs, the majority (n=35) were operating under a UL FOA (such as PAR-15-304). Of these 40% were in the large category, 23% in the middle category, and 37% in the small category (Figure 1). Of the 27 hubs operating under the UM FOA (PAR-21-293), 37% were in the largest category, 15% in the next smaller category, 22% in the next smaller category, and 26% in the smallest category (Figure 2). The different FOAs used different size category parameters making comparison between the two categories. The figures include the size category parameters for each FOA.

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Figure 1: Responding CTSA hubs under UL funding by size category

Figure 2: Responding CTSA hubs under UM funding by size category

CTSA Hub Partnerships

The 2021 CTSA Program Evaluator survey included questions asking respondents to describe the types of partnerships engaged with the CTSA hub. The 2024 survey included a slightly modified version of the question.

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Of the respondents, 40% indicated they operated as a single entity. The 60% indicating being part of a multiple entity hub reported a variety of partnerships (based on RPPR definition). Of those indicating only one partner, the most frequently reported partner was a medical school followed by academic health centers. For those indicating more than one partner, the most frequently reported partner was a hospital system, followed by a university and an academic medical center. Almost all partner types mentioned were academic or health care system focused.

Evaluation Team

Engagement of the Evaluation Team with other teams in the Hub is a critical part of fulfilling the evaluation role. Respondents were asked to select which of the following statements are the primary ways in which your Evaluation Team interacts with these various groups within your CTSA. Most reported using formal standing meetings (Table 1).

Table 1: Evaluation team interactions with other groups

<i>Interaction Type</i>	<i>Ad hoc/as needed meetings</i>		<i>Formal Standing meeting</i>		<i>Missing</i>
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	
<i>Your Principal Investigator (PI)</i>	16	25.8	46	74.2	0
<i>Your CTSA Admin Staff (excluding PI)</i>	7	11.5	54	88.5	1
<i>Program Staff</i>	25	41.7	35	58.3	4
<i>An Evaluation Committee</i>	28	48.3	30	51.7	1

In previous surveys of the CTSA hub evaluators, the direct connection with hub leadership was identified as an issue of concern. Respondents were asked how often their Evaluation Team meets one-on-one with hub leadership defined as PI, Co-Is, Core/Program Leaders, Executive Team etc. (Table 2).

Table 2: Frequency of meeting with hub leadership

<i>Meeting Frequency with PI</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Weekly</i>	11	18.0
<i>Twice a month</i>	10	16.4
<i>Monthly</i>	20	32.8
<i>Quarterly</i>	12	19.7
<i>Once a year</i>	3	4.9
<i>Other</i>	5	8.2
<i>Missing =1</i>		
<i>Other Meeting Frequency included: Ad hoc with XX, with the ED (YY) I meet every week, every other month (n=2), as needed (n=2)</i>		

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An ongoing issue for hub evaluation is the engagement of the Evaluation Team on hub leadership groups. Respondents were asked if their Evaluation team is represented on your hub's Leadership Committee (Table 3).

Table 3: Evaluation team representation on hub leadership committee

Steering Committee	Percent
Yes	91.9
No	8.1

The survey asked respondents to report the number of individuals on the Evaluation Team regardless of the percent of time spent providing evaluation services (Table 4).

Table 4: Number of individuals on evaluation team

Total Number of individuals on Evaluation team	Percent
1	8.2
2	32.8
3	29.5
4	13.1
5	8.2
6 or more	8.2
Missing=1	

Respondents were asked to report the % FTE (Full Time Equivalent) for each member of their Evaluation Team using the "best fit" for the team by position type (Table 5).

Table 5: Percent FTE by evaluation team positions

%FTE	n	Minimum Percent	Maximum Percent	Mean Percent	Mean FTE	StD
Lead	55	0.8	100	36.7	.37	34.2
Co-lead	27	0	100	49.0	.49	43.6
Manager	33	0	100	60.5	.61	41.0
Staff	35	0	240	73.6	.74	63.8
Other	22	0	100	29.1	.29	34.1
Total %FTE per Hub	57	1.9	475	150.4	1.5	101.2

Note: All FTE are reported as percentages, e.g., Joe has 65% FTE, except for Mean FTE (Column 6) which is reported as FTE, e.g., Joe has .65 FTE.

Evaluation teams across CTSA most commonly consisted of 2 (32.8%) to 3 (29.5) individuals (Table 4). The median %FTE for Evaluation team leads and co-leads was 25%, while the median %FTE for evaluation managers was 75%. The median %FTE for the entire evaluation team per hub was 130% (interquartile range 95%-200% FTE). Most evaluators indicated that their evaluation team was represented in their hub's leadership committee (91.9%, n=57, Table 3). In

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terms of interaction with various groups within their CTSA, most responding evaluators had formal standing meetings with their PI(s) (74.2%, n=46) and CTSA admin staff teams (88.5%, n=54) (Table 1). Meetings with program staff and an evaluation committee were either ad hoc/as needed or formal standing committees. When asked about their meeting frequency with hub leadership, including PI(s), Co-Is, Core/Program Leaders, Executive team, monthly meetings were most common (32.8%, n=20), followed by quarterly (19.7%, n=12), weekly (18.0%, n=11), and twice a month (16.4%, n=10) meetings (Table 2).

Research Performance Progress Report (RPPR) Responsibilities

When asked who is primarily responsible for collecting the RPPR data, respondents could select multiple options, and the results were evenly divided (Table 6). The most frequent response was “Administration other than the evaluation team” (45). 36 and 35 people reported the individual programs and the evaluation team, respectively. This indicates that the RPPR is often a collaborative effort, requiring more than one individual to collect and report the information.

Table 6: RPPR responsibilities

<i>Who is primarily responsible for collecting and reporting Research Performance Progress Report (RPPR) data at your CTSA? [Check all that apply.]</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Administration (other than Evaluation Team)</i>	45	72.6
<i>Individual Programs Submits Data/Information</i>	36	58.1
<i>Evaluation Team</i>	35	56.5
<i>Other</i>	0	0

Evaluation Influence

Respondents were asked their opinion, to what extent their local CTSA evaluation data findings influence changes at their hub on the domains of performance improvement, resource allocation, and changes in CTSA hub services offered. For 60 hubs responding, the most frequent assessment of the contribution across the three domains was as some influence (Table 7, Figure 3). This pattern is similar to the results of the 2021 Evaluator Survey.

Table 7: Evaluation data findings impact on hub decisions

<i>The extent your local CTSA evaluation data findings influence changes at your hub on the following domains:</i>	<i>Not at all</i>		<i>Some Influence</i>		<i>Great Influence</i>	
	<i>Freq</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Freq</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Freq</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Performance Improvement</i>	2	3.3	41	68.3	17	28.3
<i>Resource Allocation</i>	11	18.3	43	71.7	6	10.0

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<i>Changes in CTSA Hub Services Offered</i>	8	13.3	42	70.0	10	16.7
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Note: data missing from two hubs.

Figure 3: Evaluation data impact on hub management decision

Internal Strategic Planning

The survey requested information regarding internal strategic planning methods used by the respondent's hub. The survey provided a list of internal strategic planning methods and asked if the method was used by the hub, was the method applied to the entire hub, at the core/program level, and whether the evaluation team was responsible for using the method. The survey responses indicated that there are differences in the use of strategic planning approaches within CTSA hubs, and in the responsibility of the Evaluation Team for the use of strategic planning approaches.

Overall, all strategic planning approaches are used more frequently within CTSA Programs or Cores than they are used for CTSA hubs considered as a whole. CTSA Evaluation Teams are typically responsible for the use of Evaluation Plans and Logic Models as strategic planning approaches. These findings reflect the more frequent use of strategic planning approaches within CTSA Programs and Cores as compared to across all CTSA programs and cores. CTSA Evaluation Teams are typically responsible for evaluation planning and logic modeling across CTSA hubs. Key differences include:

1. Strategic planning approaches used for the CTSA as a whole.

- Most CTSA hubs use either Evaluation Plans or Logic Models for strategic planning purposes, with all other kinds of strategic planning approaches being used by less than half of CTSA hubs.
- Between 40% and 30% of CTSA hubs use either Milestones or Business Improvement Methods, such as Lean Six Sigma, Continuous Quality Improvement approaches.

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- Less than a quarter of CTSA use other strategic planning approaches including Process Models, NCATS Common Metrics, or Balanced Scorecards approaches. Other strategic planning approaches in use by less than 5% of CTSA include Key Driver Diagrams, Key Performance Indicators, and the Translational Science Benefits Model.
- 2. Strategic planning approaches used within CTSA Programs or Cores**
- Most CTSA Programs and Cores use either Evaluation Plans or Logic Models for strategic planning purposes, with 70% using Milestones for strategic planning purposes.
 - Process Models or Business Improvement Methods, such as Lean Six Sigma, Continuous Quality Improvement approaches, are used by just under half of CTSA programs or Cores (46% and 48% respectively).
 - The use of NCATS Common Metrics and Balanced Scorecards within CTSA Programs or Cores is less common, but these two approaches are used more frequently within programs or cores than they are across programs or cores. These two strategic planning approaches are no longer in use at most CTSA hubs (54% and 69% respectively)
- 3. CTSA Evaluation Teams** are responsible for particular strategic planning approaches.
- Most CTSA Evaluation teams are responsible for using either Evaluation Plans or Logic Models for strategic planning purposes (62% and 74% respectively).
 - 43% of CTSA Evaluation Teams are responsible for Business Improvement Methods, such as Lean Six Sigma, Continuous Quality Improvement approaches, and roughly a third (35%) are responsible for the use of Milestones.
 - A quarter (25%) of CTSA Evaluation Teams are responsible for the use of CTSA Common Metrics, and 20% are responsible for the use of Process Models.

Evaluation Tools and Methods

As part of describing the evaluation processes and methods used across CTSA hubs, respondents were provided a list of evaluation tools and modes of analysis and asked to indicate whether your CTSA used any of these methods in the past year, then indicate if tool/method was used at the hub-level and/or used at the Program/Component-level. Respondents could select all that apply. This question was significantly revised from prior survey administrations to reflect current trends in evaluation and reduce the length of response choices by eliminating tools that were reported to be rarely utilized in prior surveys.

Specifically, responding evaluators were asked about whether they used 13 different evaluation tools/methods at the hub or program/component level (Table 8). The three most used tools/methods at the hub level were bibliometric analysis (71.0%, n=44), database development, data extraction from existing records (69.4, n=43), and grants analysis (66.1%, n=41). The three most used tools/methods on the program/component level were quantitative analysis (e.g., Surveys, statistical methods, sampling techniques, 82.3%, n=51), qualitative analysis (e.g., case studies, focus groups, process tracing, Atlas (software), interviews, 75.8%, n=47), and analytics (e.g., webpages, recruitment and engagement, online courses, 71.0%, n=44) (Figure 4). The three least used tools/methods in general were quality improvement methods (e.g., Lean Six Sigma, Shewhart Cycle, 46.8%, n=29), Machine Learning and AI approaches (45.2%, n=28), and social media analysis (38.7%, n=24) (Figure 5). In open-ended responses regarding what other tools/methods evaluators used besides the 13 tools/methods listed, Objectives and Key Results (OKR) and Turn the Curve methodology were mentioned.

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Table 8: Evaluation tools and models used by most frequently reported use at program level

	<i>Did not use in the past year</i>	<i>Used at Hub level</i>	<i>Used at Program/Component Level</i>
	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Quantitative Analysis (Surveys, statistical methods, sampling techniques)	1.6	61.3	82.3
Qualitative Analysis (case studies, focus groups, process tracing, Atlas (software), interviews)	4.8	45.2	75.8
Analytics (e.g., webpages, recruitment and engagement, online courses)	8.1	54.8	71
Data Visualization (e.g., Dashboards, Infographics)	9.7	64.5	66.1
Database Development, Data Extraction from existing records	8.1	69.4	64.5
Impact Analysis	14.5	54.8	50
Machine Learning and AI Approaches	45.2	16.1	45.2
Bibliometric analysis	14.5	71	45.2
Grants analysis	17.7	66.1	43.6
Advanced Evaluation Designs (e.g., Mixed Methods, Experimental or Quasi-experimental Methods)	37.1	25.8	43.6
Quality Improvement Methods (Lean Six Sigma, Shewhart Cycle, etc.)	46.8	17.7	38.7
Financial Analysis (Cost-benefit, cost-effectiveness, ROI)	32.3	38.7	37.1

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Social Media analysis	38.7	43.6	24.2
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Figure 4: Evaluation tools and models by reported percentage using at the program level

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Figure 5: Tools and models by reported as not being used in the last year by the evaluation team

Note: quality improvement methods, ML & AI approaches, social media analysis, advanced evaluation methods and financial analysis are least often used by hubs.

Collaboration

The survey included questions regarding how and with whom the Evaluation Team collaborated in the last 12 months. Collaboration was defined as any process where the Evaluation teams are working with other evaluators, CTSA staff, other Cores (i.e. Programs/Components/Units) staff, or other CTSA Hubs, etc. to jointly produce or create any given output or deliverable.

Collaboration within the hub and with external partners is an important element of conducting evaluation efforts for the hub. Respondents were asked to provide data on collaborations already underway, planned, or considered.

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Within hub

Overall, nearly all hubs (79%) reported having formed formal collaborations with other programs or cores within their hub. Four hubs had no reported activity in this area and another four had only considered collaborating, collectively representing 13% of responding hubs.

This was a check all that apply response question. Four hubs (8%) indicated that they had no internal collaborations or had not considered having. Of the 17 (27%) who indicated that they had considered all but four had moved to either communicating and/or forming formal collaborations. There were 13 (21%) that checked all three response options (considering, communicating and formal collaboration established). 49 (79%) of hubs indicated that they had formal collaborations

With other hubs

Overall, two-thirds of hubs (66%) have formed formal collaborations with other hubs. This was a check all that apply response question. 5 hubs (9%) indicated that they had no internal collaborations or had not considered forming formal collaborations. Four (6%) have considered but not moved beyond considering forming external collaborations.

Impact Evaluation

Hubs face an increasing emphasis on tracking, assessing and reporting on how hub resources and services have contributed to outcomes and how these resources and services have added value to the public and funders. The survey included a series of questions on the importance of impact evaluation in the hubs and methods used to track, assess, and report those outcomes and impacts.

Table 9: Impact evaluation as hub priority

<i>Was impact evaluation established as a priority in your organization's most recent CTSA application or renewal?</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Yes</i>	82.0
<i>No</i>	15.0
<i>Frequency Missing = 2</i>	3.0

Respondents were asked if impact evaluation had been established as a priority in their organization's most recent CTSA application or renewal (Table 9, Figure 6). Eighty-two percent of responding hubs indicated that impact evaluation has been established as a priority, 57% of those hubs were UL grants and 43% were UM grants. Of the 15% who had not established impact evaluation as a priority, four were UM grants and five were UL grants. For the 3% (n=2) that did not respond to the question, it was an even split between UM and UL (1 each).

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Figure 6: Frequency of impact evaluation as a hub priority

Respondents were asked who, at their hub, is currently or will be responsible for impact data collection. Check all that apply options included: A) Evaluation team, B) PI(s), C)CTSA Administrative Staff (not including the PI), D) other program leaders; and E) Other (with the option to specify).

Table 10: Responsibility for hub impact data collection

<i>Who is currently or will be responsible for impact data collection? Check all that apply</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Evaluation Team</i>	54	87.1
<i>PI(s)</i>	11	17.7
<i>CTSA Admin Staff (not PI)</i>	31	50.0
<i>Other program leaders</i>	31	50.0
<i>Other</i>	4	6.5
<i>None selected</i>	4	—

Respondents reported that 87% of the time the Evaluation team is or will be at least in part responsible for collecting impact data, followed but CTSA Administrative Staff (not including the PI) and other program leaders (both selected by 50% of the respondents) (Table 10). The median number of parties responsible for impact data collection was 2. This was true for hubs that replied both “No” and “Yes” when asked if impact was a priority. Note that of the 9 hubs that replied “No” 77% (7 out of 9) still had staff with some responsibility in the area of impact data collection. Not being a priority does not mean there is no evaluation of impact.

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Types of Impact Data Collaboration

Examining the different combinations of collaboration to collect impact data for hubs more closely (Figure 7), showed that the most common set-up has or will have evaluation teams solely responsible for collecting impact data (17 hubs). Next, the second most common combination was evaluation teams in collaboration with CTSA administrative staff (not including PI) and other program leaders (11 hubs). The third most common combination included evaluation teams, PI(s), CTSA administrative staff, and other program leaders (9 hubs). Only four hubs did not include evaluation teams in their current or planned efforts to collect impact data.

Figure 7: Current responsibility for hub impact data collection

Note: Includes combinations with n=1, but grouped into other with and without the eval team (A); Combinations of groups sorted by frequency (A=evaluation team; B= PI; C=CTSA admin staff; D=other program leaders; E=others)

Respondents were asked if their hub had established a standard set of measures used by components/cores/programs to track and assess impact of hub efforts. Although over 80% reported impact evaluation is a priority for their hub, just under 50% reported having established impact measures. Table 11 summarizes the types of impact goals or metrics established.

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Table 11: Impact Goals and Metrics

Category	Impact Goals or Metrics
<p><i>Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) – or other framework with established metrics</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Widespread adoption of TSBM as the primary framework for impact assessment. ● Applied at both program/core level and hub Level. ● Many hubs are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collecting TSBM data annually (sometimes by program type, e.g., KL2 every year, others every 2 years). ○ Using TSBM surveys, publication analysis, ROI analysis, bibliometric analysis. ○ Coding success stories and linking TSBM domains/categories to intake, progress reporting, and alumni follow-up. ● Some hubs are combining TSBM with RE-AIM or other frameworks. ● A few hubs are building evaluation plans to align with TSBM domains.
<p><i>Standardization and Core/Program-Specific Metrics</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standardized measures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Demographic and socio-demographic data. ○ Satisfaction surveys/client experience (sometimes standardized across programs). ○ Standard tools for tracking publications, grants, collaborations, clinical research competencies – to enable cross-program comparability. ● Program/core-specific metrics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Metrics tied directly to program aims and KPIs. ○ Activity vs. impact templates separating process data (applications, participants, hours, trainings) from outcomes (funding, publications, collaborations). ○ Logic models, key driver diagrams, and causal pathways used to define and organize metrics. ○ Emphasis on feasibility and utility of metrics—must be practical for program improvement.

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<p><i>Evaluation Processes and Infrastructure</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralized systems to track client services, collaborations, publications, and grants. • Use of annual/quarterly cycles for reporting • Evaluation plans developed in collaboration with program resources. • Benchmarks against peer CTSA hubs. • Formal logic model processes to track accomplishments and resource use. • Combining qualitative and quantitative data (e.g., interviews, surveys, metrics). • Metrics inform program improvement, not just reporting.
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Respondents were asked to identify challenges encountered in conducting impact evaluation studies (Table 12). The most common challenges reported included the quality of data reporting from surveys, the ability to link impact to hub activities, and infrastructure needed to collect and analyze data regarding impact.

Table 12: Impact Evaluation Challenges

Category	Impact Evaluation Challenges
<p><i>Data Quality & Response Rate Issues</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low/inconsistent survey response rates, especially for TSBM surveys and post-program follow-ups. • Concerns about TSBM data quality due to self-reporting and incomplete verification. • Difficulty getting data from investigators after support ends or from multiple programs with diverse practices. • Balancing detail vs. brevity when asking for TSBM data (too many indicators, overwhelming forms).
<p><i>Attribution & Defining Impact</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard to distinguish outputs from true impacts. • Attribution challenges: which outcomes can be linked to hub/program support? • Lag times before impacts (policy, economic, clinical, community) become visible. • Difficulty categorizing impacts (e.g., clinical vs. community; overlapping benefits). • Struggle with process vs. impact measures and tying short-term outcomes to long-term impact.

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<p><i>Conceptual & Framework Challenges (TSBM)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of TSBM indicators make it good for nuance, but hard to integrate into reporting. • Uncertainty about TSBM's fit for their hub; some leaders/EACs question its value. • TSBM seen as a case study framework, not a comprehensive hub-wide tool • Lack of clear definition of impact across programs, making standardization difficult.
<p><i>Resource & Capacity Limitations</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time! Staffing shortages, limited bandwidth, no dedicated evaluation team, and insufficient resources to handle complex evaluations with multiple data sources. • Evaluation teams often new or small, still developing procedures or databases. • Limited funding for evaluation work in faculty grants or hub budgets. • Competing demands: "so much to do," making prioritization difficult. • Lack of systems / databases for tracking activities, outputs, and impacts. • Struggles with visualizing / presenting TSBM data in a digestible way.

Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)

The Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) is a widely used framework for tracking, documenting, and reporting the outcomes and impacts related to the use of hub resources and services. The survey included a series of questions to gather updated data on the use of the TSBM and the contribution the Evaluation Team makes to the use of the TSBM framework.

Respondents were asked to assess the extent their evaluation team contributed directly to evaluations of your CTSA's impact on any of the following Translational Science Benefit Model (TSBM) domains (Figure 8) Evaluation teams were most involved in assessing Policy and Economic impacts, while Clinical Measures had the least extensive contributions. In addition, the overall contribution distribution shows that 50.3% of responses were "Moderate" or "Extensive," meaning evaluation teams were fairly engaged. Further, most respondents reported at least "Somewhat" contributing to evaluations in the four domains. Policy and Economic domains received the highest "Extensive" contributions and Clinical Measures had the lowest "Extensive" contributions, with higher "Very Limited" and "None" responses.

General Patterns Across Categories

- Policy Measures had the strongest reported contribution, with 21 respondents selecting "Extensive."
- Community and Economic Measures had similar distributions, with most responses clustering in the "Somewhat" and "Moderate" range.
- Clinical Measures had the highest proportion of "Very Limited" and "None" responses, suggesting weaker contributions in this domain.

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Most Common Response:

- Community Measures received the highest "Somewhat" (22 responses).
- Policy Measures had the most "Extensive" responses (21 responses).

Least Common Response:

- "None" was least frequent for Community Measures (only 6 responses).
- "Very Limited" responses were relatively low in Economic & Policy Measures.

Overall Trends:

- Community and Policy Measures tend to have higher "Moderate" and "Extensive" ratings.
- Economic Measures and Clinical Measures have a more even distribution across response options.

Figure 8: Evaluation team engagement in hub impact assessment by TSBM domains

What This Means for Evaluation Teams

- Policy-related evaluations are a clear strength, so the team could share best practices from these evaluations.
- Clinical Measures need more involvement, possibly requiring additional collaboration with researchers and clinicians.
- Since "Somewhat" was the most common response overall, there may be capacity gaps or areas where evaluation teams could enhance their contributions.

Evaluation Reports and Outputs

Evaluation teams create reports to document hub activities, processes, and accomplishments as part of their contribution to hub success. The survey included an opportunity for respondents to

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provide information regarding the types of reports generated, how findings from those reports are disseminated, and the primary users of those reports. Respondents were asked what evaluation-related outputs their Evaluation Team produces.

The three most commonly mentioned evaluation outputs are evaluation reports/summaries (95%, n=59) and presentations (84%, n=52), followed by manuscripts (63%, n=52) (Table 13). Social media posts, whitepapers, and newsletters were least often produced by evaluation teams. In open-ended responses, evaluators also mentioned dashboards, data reports, memos, investigator impact videos, and posters. Eight hubs (12.8%) selected “Other” with the opportunity to specify. One hub stated that they create investigator impact videos.

Table 13: Evaluation-related outputs by evaluation team

<i>What evaluation-related outputs does your Evaluation Team produce?</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Evaluation reports and summaries</i>	95.2
<i>Presentations</i>	83.9
<i>Manuscripts</i>	62.9
<i>Flyers/handouts</i>	16.1
<i>Newsletters</i>	14.5
<i>White papers</i>	12.9
<i>Social media posts</i>	8.1

Evaluation outputs are most often disseminated through meetings with the Hub PI/leadership team (95.1%, n=59), followed by peer review publications (61.3%, n=38), Internal Advisory board meetings (59.7%, n=37), and emails and conferences (both 58.1%, n=36) (Table 14). Users of evaluation outputs vary by output type (Table 15). The most common users of reports and summaries are CTSA hub (90.3%, n=56) and CTSA core (82.4%, n=51) leadership. Users of manuscripts were most commonly external researchers (53.2%, n=33) and hub leadership (45.2%, n=28). Notably, all user types were selected much less often to be users of social media posts, flyers/handouts, and newsletters.

Table 14: Dissemination methods for evaluation outputs

<i>Dissemination Method</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Meetings with PI/Leadership team</i>	95.2
<i>Peer-review publications</i>	61.3
<i>Internal Advisory Board meeting</i>	59.7
<i>Email</i>	58.1
<i>Professional conferences</i>	58.1
<i>Community oriented conferences/presentations</i>	40.3
<i>CTSA website</i>	37.1
<i>Word of mouth</i>	37.1
<i>Social media platforms</i>	22.6
<i>White paper repository</i>	1.6

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Table 15: Evaluation outputs users

<i>Who are the Users of your evaluation outputs?</i>	<i>CTSA HUB Leadership</i>	<i>CTSA Core Leadership</i>	<i>External researcher</i>	<i>Community Members</i>	<i>Others</i>	<i>Unsure</i>	<i>Number of Hubs producing evaluation output</i>
	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
<i>Evaluation reports and summaries</i>	90.3	82.3	11.0	24.2	6.5	3.2	59
<i>Flyers/handouts</i>	9.7	8.1	3.3	3.3	0	3.3	10
<i>White papers</i>	9.7	9.7	1.6	3.3	3.3	0	8
<i>Manuscripts</i>	45.2	35.5	53.2	12.9	9.7	3.2	39
<i>Social media posts</i>	4.8	3.2	4.8	4.8	1.6	0	5
<i>Presentations</i>	69.4	64.5	45.2	35.5	19.4	0	52
<i>Newsletters</i>	9.7	9.7	8.1	6.5	8.1	1.6	9
<i>Other, please specify</i>	1.6	1.6	0	0	0	1.6	8

Other evaluation output users mentioned included (n=1): “Our work to disseminate to external researchers and community has been limited so far but is a goal of our renewal”

Awareness of and use of Evaluation teams outputs competes with a plethora of information sources communicating information about scientific discovery and hub information. The survey asked if the evaluation team works with a communication specialist to create evaluation outputs to disseminate findings.

When asked about whether evaluation teams worked with a communication specialist to create evaluation outputs to their disseminate findings, 58% (n=35) stated that they did not with a majority indicating that they would like to work with a communication specialist (Table 16). Evaluators were able to discuss formal communication strategies they use for their evaluation outputs in open-ended responses. Twenty-nine responses were provided (46.8%). Responses varied from working with hub communication teams to develop impact stories, coordinate social media presence, and improve readability of outputs to having set design principles for evaluation outputs. It was also mentioned that some evaluation teams have little to no support for communication strategies.

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Table 16: Evaluation team works with communication specialist to disseminate findings

<i>Work with communication specialist</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Yes	41.7
No, but would like to	38.3
No	20.0
Missing =2	

In addition to selecting communications strategies from a list of options, respondents were asked what, if any, formal communication strategies they used for their evaluation outputs (Table 17).

Table 17: Communications and evaluation coordination

<i>Category/Theme</i>	<i>Comments</i>
<i>Reports</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In prior years, we have created an annual report that was publicized on our website. We plan to continue this tradition in 2025. We post stories about CTSI accomplishments on our website and social media. • We use white papers, presentations to different audiences, our website, social media, and TSBM profiles that will be posted on [hub name] website as well as ours. • We have minimal support for this. We do produce an annual report with our communication team. Much more is needed.
<i>Meetings/Collaboration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We coordinate with the Communications team to improve the readability for reports that will be distributed outside the hub. We also work with the Communications team to identify examples of how evaluation outputs have been used. • Collaboration with communications lead to develop newsletter articles fit for general audience
<i>Social Media</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We use a lot of the evaluation outputs in our RPPRs. in addition to that, in executive meetings, social media, our hub's newsletter.
<i>Website</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We have two communication managers on staff that work with us to promote case studies, publications, and other outcome metrics via presentations, newsletter and our website. • Reports and write-ups on our CTSA hub's website, as well as social media posts.

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<i>Data Visualization</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We have developed a set of design principles that we use for all of our evaluation outputs. These emphasize writing for specific audiences, using inclusive and non-technical language, emphasizing brief reports, large use of visuals, using consistent design (e.g., color) and branding, etc. • Communicate results through graphs and figures whenever possible and one-page executive summaries of longer reports. • Engage professional infographics/designer to create professional infographics.
<i>Planning and Strategy</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The communications team has a formal plan to which we contribute data and stories. • We briefly had a part-time communication specialist who is not longer working at our institution. The evaluation team and administration will work together on communication strategies going forward.
<i>RPPR</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We use a lot of the evaluation outputs in our RPPRs. in addition to that, in executive meetings, social media, our hub's newsletter. • RPPRs, monthly internal and external newsletters to interested groups (funders, awardees, collaborating partner schools and institutes). There is not a clear audience for who would be the recipient of annual reports (for example) and the capacity to build beyond typical reporting to EAC, IAC, RPPR, NIH, our Program Officer, is limited.
<i>TSBM</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We use white papers, presentations to different audiences, our website, social media, and TSBM profiles that will be posted on [hub name] website as well as ours. • The communication manager was consulted to help format a TSBM case study paper.

Dissemination and Implementation

NIH and NCATS have placed increasing emphasis on the dissemination and implementation (D&I) of research findings. The survey asked respondents to provide information regarding the Evaluation Team contribution to dissemination and implementation of research findings generated at their hub.

Over half (57%) of responding hubs (n=60) indicated involvement in hub D&I activities. About a third (30%) indicated no involvement. Involvement was not related to grant type (UM/UL).

The main themes in these statements revolve around Dissemination and Implementation (D&I) Science, Evaluation, and Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI) (Table 18). Key themes include:

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Table 18: Responses regarding evaluation team engagement with hub dissemination and implementation activities

Category/Theme	Comments
<i>Integration of Dissemination & Implementation (D&I) Science in Evaluation</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation teams work closely with D&I centers and leadership to assess the effectiveness of implementation efforts. • Tracking and assessing uptake, impact, and outcomes of D&I strategies. • Collaboration between evaluation and D&I teams to ensure implementation projects are measured and improved.
<i>Development of D&I Resources and Support Structures</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of D&I cores within hubs to guide implementation efforts. • Development of processes, tools, and scoring metrics for D&I pilot grants. • Conducting monthly seminars, workshops, and office hours to support investigators in applying D&I principles
<i>Collaboration Across Teams and Institutions</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular coordination with Center for Dissemination and Implementation Science (CDIS) and other research units. • Linking Pilot Program teams with implementation scientists and evaluation experts. • Participation in D&I advisory groups, strategic planning, and grant proposal development.
<i>Evaluation and Measurement of D&I Initiatives</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting qualitative research, key informant interviews, and surveys on knowledge dissemination and uptake. • Using the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) for structuring evaluation approaches. • Monitoring and analyzing implementation efforts to ensure alignment with core translational research goals.
<i>Strategic Planning and Leadership in D&I</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D&I efforts are woven into broader CTSA grant activities to support translational science. • Evaluation directors and leaders serve as liaisons between evaluation, D&I, and hub leadership. • Emphasis on Innovate, Implement, and Include as core guiding principles.
<i>Knowledge Translation and Communication</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translating evaluation findings into accessible formats for external audiences. • Developing user-friendly dashboards and web pages for dissemination of findings. • Engaging in informal communication and strategic meetings with leadership teams.

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<i>Equity and Impact-Driven Implementation</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on Implementation for Impact & Equity as a key optional function. • Ensuring D&I efforts promote equitable access and benefit diverse communities.
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Overall, these statements reflect a structured, strategic, and collaborative approach to embedding D&I science into evaluation efforts, ensuring continuous improvement, informed decision-making, and broad dissemination of translational research findings.

Translational Science Data Collection

With the new FOA, attention to addressing translational science, the processes related to the conduct of translational research, has increased. The survey included questions to collect data regarding how hubs are addressing translational science.

Table 19: Translational science data collection

<i>Does your CTSA hub collect data/metrics specific to clinical and translational sciences (the process of clinical and translational research)</i>	<i>Percent</i>
<i>Yes</i>	62.9
<i>No</i>	17.7
<i>Not Sure</i>	16.1
<i>Missing</i>	3.2
<i>Total</i>	

Table 19 shows the percentage of CTSA hubs collecting data or metrics related to clinical and translational sciences. The majority (62.9%) indicated that they were collecting some data. 16.1% were unsure, and 17.7% said the data was not collected. In an open-ended question about the evaluation methods used to collect clinical and translational science data, responses were categorized by topic in Table 20.

Respondents provide 20 different evaluation methods for collecting clinical and translational science data. The most common response was the Translational Science Benefits Model, with 40 hubs reporting its use. However, several respondents noted that the TSBM work was early in its implementation or planned for the next grant cycle. The next most common method was Logic Models (31 respondents), followed by the RE-AIM evaluation framework and Quality Improvement models such as PDSA or CQI, use of case studies and challenges/barriers addressed. Numerous other methods such as LSAS-I (Longitudinal Scientific Achievement & Impact Survey), process maps, mixed methods, causal pathway, custom questions about products and processes as well as implementation activities, CIPP (context, inputs, process, and product), concept frameworks, and home-grown models and methods were reported. Of note, most respondents listed a combination of methods, for example, “TSBM & Logic models” or “TSBM, Logic models, and other biomedical impact frameworks,” and indicated that the hub utilizes multiple methods in its translational science evaluation.

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Table 20: Translational science methods

<i>What evaluation methods does your hub use related to clinical and translational science (e.g., TSBM, Logic models, Translational Science Impact Scale, etc.?)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
<i>TSBM</i>	40
<i>Logic models</i>	31
<i>RE-AIM</i>	3
<i>PDSA/CQI</i>	2
<i>Case studies</i>	2
<i>TS challenges/barriers addressed</i>	2

An open-ended comment box was provided for respondents to provide additional details on the types of evaluation questions asked or the translational science data collected. The responses were categorized into five types of data sources (surveys, qualitative data, grant applications, publications, or funding data, and institutional or other reporting mechanisms). Table 21 provides examples of the different data sources used by the CTSA evaluators and illustrates the need for mixed and multi-methods to capture the work in the hubs. For example, the evaluator may use a survey or reporting tool to collect information from investigators or pilot recipients. But then must code or categorize the data into the TSBM categories to assess impact.

Table 21: Examples of evaluation questions or data collected about clinical and translational science.

<i>Data Sources</i>	<i>Examples</i>
<i>Surveys</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General use of biennial surveys based on TSBM to assess CTS impact and addressing CTS barriers; bie • Specific use to assess stakeholders access to CTSA services; obtain pilot grant awardees data; from other CTSA program users; KL2 trainees (examples of TSBM categories). May be annual or biennial
<i>Qualitative</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitators and challenges encountered by successful translational scientists. • Case studies, interviews • Across T0-T4 investigators collect TSBM information through longitudinal interviews (re. CTR and CTS) with high-impact project PI's
<i>Grant applications</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess grants and papers associated with CTSA activities, count of pilot program submissions with TS • Assess goal completion based on annual reports and over time.
<i>Publication & Funding Data</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benchmarking hub's CTS publications with other hubs including bibliometrics; frequencies of publications, pilot funding, presentations. • Project/pilot: findings of TS projects; ROI
<i>Institutional Data or Other Reporting</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainees/pilot awardee provide data on their work's alignment with TSBM and/or TS; ask at application and/or during/after

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<i>Mechanism</i>	<p>implementation as some TS is unanticipated at time of project proposal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site activation metrics IRB times; some funded projects' outcomes tracked more closely (e.g. Pilots; Element E)
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Finally, several respondents noted using specific translational science questions to assess impact, challenges, and barriers (Table 22).

Table 22: Evaluation Questions or Topics

Category	Comments
<i>Translational Science Criteria & Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of translational science checklist questions (e.g., overcoming barriers, generalizability, efficiency/effectiveness). • Requirement for both scientific and translational science hypotheses. • Layman's terms descriptions for accessibility. • Retrospective coding of prior pilot awards.
<i>Evaluation & Impact Measurement</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation and dissemination of hub engagement. • Development of specific evaluation questions across domains: dissemination & implementation (D&I), clinical training, clinical trials, team science, health equity, and impact evaluation. • Identifying facilitators and barriers to conducting translational research
<i>Education & Training</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embedding translational science concepts and competencies into educational programs. • Engaging trainees and scholars in translational science questions and practices (though not always systematically reported). • Mentorship, collaboration planning, and internal training of PIs and staff.
<i>Research & Program Activities</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of translational science principles in pilot awards, resource activities, community engagement, and workforce development. • Research projects emphasizing team science, collaboration, learning health systems, and evaluation techniques.
<i>Organizational Development & Capacity Building</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building processes to engage scientists systematically in clinical and translational science (CTS). • Preparing for future funding phases (e.g., UM1). • Addressing internal challenges ("digging out of a bit of a mess") while developing structured approaches.
<i>Cross-Cutting Priorities</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale, innovation, and populations impacted/accommodated. • Emphasis on interdisciplinarity and team science as guiding values.

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Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI) and Evaluation

An element of the CTSA program focus is on improving processes related to the conduct of translational research (translational science) as well as the efficiency of hub processes and services. The survey asked respondents for information regarding the engagement of the Evaluation Team on continuous quality improvement (CQI) strategies and processes within their hub.

Evaluation team involvement in hub CQI work

Nearly all hubs (79%) indicated that CQI was a priority for their hub (Figure 9). Among those nearly all (73%) were somewhat or extremely concerned about its impact on their bandwidth for evaluation work.

Just under half (46%) of hubs who reported involvement in CQI activities (n=59) indicated a role in directing their hub's CQI program (Figure 10). Three quarters (76%) of the 59 hubs reported consulting on CQI activities. Around 60% (of the 59) were involved with CQI planning and data collection. Involvement did not differ by grant type (UM/UL). It is interesting to note that in reporting evaluation tools used, nearly one-half of all respondents responded that they did not use CQI tools (see Table 8 and Figure 5).

Figure 9: Continuous Quality Improvement (CQI) as hub priority

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Figure 10: Evaluation team role in hub CQI (frequencies)

Respondents were asked to report issues with evaluation role in CQI processes at their hub. Overall, the statements reflect a tension between the desire to implement CQI effectively and the practical constraints of staffing, time, and resources (Table 22). Some teams have well-integrated CQI processes, while others are still developing frameworks and seeking more guidance.

In addition, the statements reflect a broad commitment to CQI across different aspects of clinical and translational research, with a focus on efficiency, data-driven decision-making, and continuous process improvement. However, challenges remain in terms of staffing, standardization, and full integration into institutional workflows.

Table 23: Reported CQI issues

Category/Theme	Comments
<i>CQI as a Priority vs. Competing Demands</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While CQI is becoming more of a priority, other evaluation efforts (e.g., impact evaluation) also require significant attention. Struggle to balance CQI with other responsibilities. • Some hubs are still in the process of developing CQI mechanisms, while others have a structured approach in place.

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<p><i>Leadership, Institutional Support</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong leadership support is crucial for CQI success, but commitment varies across institutions. • Some teams note that leadership is aware of the burden CQI brings but still expects it to be implemented. • Need for clear communication from leadership on priorities and expectations for CQI. • Those newer to CQI still developing frameworks, while others have completed multiple projects. • Implementation varies across institutions, with some evaluation teams primarily supporting the pre-evaluation phase while leaving implementation to Cores. • Ongoing efforts to shift CQI responsibilities from evaluation teams to program managers for sustainability. • Some institutions have dedicated administrative support for CQI, while others rely on ad-hoc efforts. • Institutional leadership plays a key role in prioritizing and integrating CQI into research and evaluation workflows.
<p><i>Complexity and Time-Intensiveness of CQI</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CQI is recognized as complex, resource-intensive, and time-consuming. • Some teams express concerns that CQI can take away time from other essential evaluation tasks. • Training and capacity building (e.g., Lean Six Sigma, train-the-trainer models) are being used to distribute CQI workload.
<p><i>Resource Constraints, Capacity Challenges and Staffing Issues</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited staffing, time constraints, and competing priorities impact CQI implementation small and understaffed teams, creating bandwidth issues making it difficult to allocate significant time to CQI; Hiring delays and limited FTEs (Full-Time Equivalents).
<p><i>Frameworks and Methodologies</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Lean Six Sigma, PDSA (Plan-Do-Study-Act) cycles, and root cause analysis. • Some hubs are in the early stages of CQI implementation, while others have structured programs in place. • Evaluation teams are exploring CQI methodologies, often starting with internal processes before expanding.
<p><i>Data Collection and Evaluation Processes</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efforts to improve and streamline data collection, tracking, and visualization. • Use of qualitative interviews, surveys, and focus groups to inform program improvements. • Enhancing hub-wide data management, evaluation mechanisms, and feedback loops. • Standardization and integration of Common Metrics across programs. • Continuous data collection required for CQI considered burdensome for small teams.

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<i>Variation in CQI Implementation and Integration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some teams have fully integrated CQI into evaluation processes, while others struggle to define clear mechanisms. • CQI efforts can be uneven across different cores/teams. • There is a need for better guidance on what a CQI program should entail.
<i>Efforts to Streamline and Formalize CQI</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teams are working on formalizing CQI processes to make them more sustainable. • Implementing structured approaches such as stacked meeting schedules and improved project management. • Shifting CQI responsibilities to program managers instead of evaluation teams.
<i>Clinical and Translational Research</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving processes and resources related to clinical trials, participant recruitment, stakeholder/community engagement and informed consent compliance. • Enhancing service delivery in Clinical Research Centers. • Process evaluation of training programs related to Team Science and grant writing.
<i>Program and Service Optimization</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Streamlining and improving various internal and external evaluation and research support services. • Development of web-based tools, dashboards, and patient portals for improved accessibility. • Enhancing hub service requisition systems, training materials, and job aids

Learning Health Systems

CTSA evaluators have been engaged in a discussion group, now working group, to assess the engagement of CTSA hubs with learning health system (LHS) efforts of hub partners. LHSs can serve a significant role in moving discoveries into medical practice and to provide real world evidence of the contribution of discoveries in improving the effectiveness and efficiency of medical care. The survey provided a series of questions to gather data about current hub-LHS collaboration and the Evaluation Team’s engagement in those efforts.

Learning Health System Involvement

Overall, evaluation team involvement in LHS work is limited. There was no pattern across hub size or type of award (UM/UL). Only one-third (29%) indicated that their evaluation team currently participates in or supports any LHS activity. While 9 (14%) were not sure if their evaluation team was involved, half (52%) of the responding hubs indicated that they were not involved in LHS work.

Evaluator Needs

The following 10 themes emerged from respondents’ comments (Table 23).

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Table 24: Reported evaluator needs

Category/Theme	Comments
<i>Examples of Evaluation Tools (N=16)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handbook of evaluation tools examples used by CTSA • List of NCATS and CTSA resources
<i>Knowledge Sharing and Mentorship (N=7)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1:1 meetings with presenters (from Evaluators meetings) • Access to peers is no substitute for talking to your peers (how best to access) • Opportunities to participate in multi-hub evaluation projects. Networking & leadership opportunities.
<i>Comprehensive Evaluation Resources (N=7)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of measures, tools, and logic models. • Examples evaluation team org charts. • Presentations on how requests for evaluation services are requested, tracked, provided. • Sample reports, dashboards, survey instruments available online for reference
<i>Orientation and Startup Guides (N=6)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Example tools, more orientation, what has been hard about getting started, overview of important NCATS/CCOS groups (including working groups). • Startup guide from other CTSA hub evaluators Including how evaluation is integrated into hub's daily operations • Orientation to the CTSA Program purpose, intro to frameworks often used, templates.
<i>Repository/Depository of Evaluation Tools (N=5)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessible Evaluation Tool Repository and Documentation.
<i>Guidance on Continuous Quality Improvement (N=3)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of evaluation tools including how different CQI processes are working; • Assistance in helping components understand the importance of evaluation and CQI and the need to collect metrics on a regular basis; how other CTSA's overcame barriers related to these items.
<i>Support for Data Collection and Management 2(N=3)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More support for data gathering from Elements and Cores. • Tools used for data collection and management. • Share tracking tools across hubs. • Need understanding of HOW/WHAT we would define as impact within the CTS rubrics (e.g. consistency of metrics? minimize inefficiency of evaluation within our own system and across hubs)
<i>Historical Context and Impact Measurement (N=2)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview on the history of how CTSA/hub evaluation methods/reporting have changed over the years

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<i>Standard Metrics and Evaluation Tools (N=2)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard metrics and evaluation tools. • Having a common set of tools accessible through the consortium, e.g., a database of surveys developed and used by CTSA evaluators, metrics, logic models, that can be used as a starting point for new CTSA/evaluators as they build their programs.
<i>Integration of AI Methods (N=1)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to integrate artificial intelligence methods such as large language models into evaluation workflows

The limited interest in use of artificial intelligence methods was of note given the rapid increase in the use of AI tools in summarizing data and reports for evaluation purposes.

Recommendations to NCATS Regarding Evaluation

CTSA evaluators’ work supports accomplishment of hub responsibilities from the FOAs. The survey provided an opportunity for respondents to share, anonymously, recommendations to NCATS that would contribute to successfully fulfilling those responsibilities. Thirty-one respondents provided suggestions for NCATS consideration. They are summarized in the following 9 themes (Table 24).

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Table 25: Recommendations to NCATS

Category/Theme	Comments
<i>Impact (N=12)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create a mechanism to showcase hubs' impact reports ● Aggregate hub data to show the national impact ● Define impact, what NCATS would like to see as impact (TSBM provides the framework & tools for discussing impact). ● Consider revising RFP so that the evaluation team's top priority is to focus on impact. For example, 1) documenting impact in multiple ways (metrics, case studies, story formats geared toward lawmakers/general public), 2) leading programs to specify the theory of change that links program activities with desired impact, 3) providing needed information and support for improvement efforts related to impact ● Support the development and assessment of evidence-based cross-hub evaluation metrics and making those data shared across hubs. ● Help hubs to understand HOW to evaluate outcomes of a thousand supported protocols annually without having capacity to investigate, or cajole every one of those protocol PIs to report, their actual research outcomes ● Share their insights on which data are most impactful for presentations on the CTSA program's impact e.g. what resonates most with Congress and the public -specific metrics, success stories, or economic benefits. ● Provide guidance on the types of evidence that justify resource allocations to ensure that evaluations are meaningful and strategically valuable.
<i>Metrics/Measures (N=10)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standardize some evaluation metrics across CTSA's; ● Emphasize longitudinal impact evaluations ● Strengthen dissemination of evaluation outcomes ● Balance universal metrics against hub-specific ones. Encourage some universal metric tracking while demonstrating diverse examples of unique metric tracking. ● Use standardized (uncomplicated) evaluation measures/metrics and apply to concepts such as health equity, community engagement, translational science, and user satisfaction
<i>Evaluation Policy (N=10)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Emphasize the need to CTSA leaders that evaluation should be a part of everyday activities and not something separate to do when reports are due ● Improve others' knowledge about the intellectual and related strategic importance and relevance of evaluation, beyond serving an administrative "bean-counting"/output-counting

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<i>Data (N=6)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregate hub data to show NCATS national impact • Create common data elements and define what impact measures they are looking for • Think about the data ecosystem and standard ways and resources for pulling data for analysis. Look at metrics and impact outside of publications, look to other data and software platforms. • Individual consultations with Coordinating Center to assist with data export and analysis
<i>RPPR (N=5)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some type of formal, structured use of the RPPRs • The progress made to analyze RPPR data is encouraging. it could be useful to have suggestions regarding data types/standards to use for reporting data through the RPPR accomplishments sections to facilitate further analysis of hub level and consortium level accomplishments and impact. The concept mapping project has significant potential to identify as standard metrics across all hubs to improve our ability to document and analyze the consortium's contribution to advancing impactful research
<i>Evaluation Resources (N=4)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More resources for evaluation. Everyone has incredible ideas but they are so slow to implement because of a tiny staff. • In my hub's case, we had a hard time justifying budget specific to Evaluation because the new FOA did not have that, although it is clear that evaluation is critical in the new FOA. My suggestion is to emphasis the role of evaluation and adjust budget.
<i>TSBM (N=3)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embed the 30 TSBM indicators into the RPPR to systematically report on knowledge transfer impact across the 60+ hubs. Consider methods for aggregating the TSBM data to assess strengths and gaps across the hubs. Begin to build a "contextual variables" database to use to examine characteristics of hubs that influence knowledge transfer, such as the number and type of interorganizational collaborations (e.g., number of multi-CTSA, county health, hub collaborations, etc.).
<i>Collaboration (N=3)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More collaboration on evaluation on the entire CTSA/NCATS approach.
<i>Others (N=6)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First More opportunities for early career individual mentoring and opportunities for them to get involved. • The role of CQI programs within CTSA hubs needs to be better detailed and supported.

III. Conclusions

The Evaluators Survey Working Group is pleased with the great cooperation rate of the 2024 CTSA Evaluators Survey. The continued high participation rate across the last several surveys

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demonstrates the hard-work, strong commitment to high-quality, methodologically sophisticated evaluation, high expertise, and collaborative nature of the Evaluation units across all hubs.

The results of the 2024 survey identified areas for further development. These include the interest in developing a set of measures that all hubs could use to assess performance at the hub level and which, if properly developed, provide NCATS with data to document consortium-wide accomplishments. Assessing impact remains a high priority issue for respondents. This could be an opportunity to develop standard measures for assessing hub impact. Respondents identified interest in accessing tools, methods, processes for conducting continuous quality improvement responsibilities. CTSA collaboration and strategies to assess collaboration impact was identified as an emerging topic. The respondents also reported interest in the development of a standard set of evaluation tools along with access to coaching in the use of those evaluation tools. This is an opportunity for the evaluator community.

The Evaluator Survey Team will review the processes and methods for conducting the evaluator survey to identify ways to refine the survey instrument design and implementation.

REDCap Citations

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Appendix 1 2024 CTSA Program Evaluator Survey Team

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